

Open Infrastructure Matters

Supporting Scholar-Led and Community-Driven Services to Advance Open Access

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Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services

A tried and tested solution to support OS infrastructure in need of immediate funding

<https://scoss.org> @scossfunding

Challenge: OA & OS infrastructure has grown in number and usage and may no longer be sustainable providing no pathway forward for continuation and further development.

Risk: Services risk stagnation, downsizing or pay walling.

Aim: Helping sustain the infrastructure to support the implementation of OS

Officially formed in early 2017, SCOSS's purpose is to provide a new co-ordinated cost-sharing framework that will ultimately enable the broader OA and OS community to support the non-commercial services on which it depends

SCOSS Members

<https://scoss.org/what-is-scoss/who-is-behind-scoss>

<https://scoss.org/what-is-scoss/governance>

How SCOSS works

SCOSS endorses infrastructure for investment

Assesses OS infrastructure
Advocates for crowd funding to sustain OS

PLEDGES to date

Total pledged
2 781 525 euros

By 258 institutions
From 19 countries

6 infrastructures

<https://scoss.org/how-it-works/current-funding-calls>

Total pledged Round 1:
2 030 200 euros

101% of target reached

42% of target

Total pledged

25

Current funding cycle

&

<https://www.doabooks.org/>

<http://www.oapen.org/home>

Pledged to date € 278 975

Remaining target € 226 025

[Download the SCOSS DOAB & OAPEN flyer](#)

<https://opencitations.net/>

Pledged to date € 307 675

Remaining target € 1 222 523

[Download the SCOSS OpenCitations flyer](#)

<https://pkp.sfu.ca/>

Pledged to date € 164 675

Remaining target € 569 972

[Download the SCOSS PKP flyer](#)

<https://scoss.org/how-it-works/current-funding-calls>

Two Infrastructures enabling Open Access Books

Eelco Ferwerda

15th Munin conference

18 November 2020

Two Infrastructures enabling Open Access Books

- Dedicated to Open Access Books
- Focus on peer reviewed monographs and edited collections
- Providing quality assurance and transparency based on peer review
- Non-profit Foundations (no ownership)
- Community based
- Developed on open source platform (DSpace)

Two Infrastructures enabling Open Access Books

OAPEN Library

- **Repository** of freely accessible academic books. An ongoing effort to build a **quality-controlled collection of Open Access books** together with publishers, research funders and libraries.
- Providing services in the areas of deposit, quality assurance, metadata enhancement, dissemination, usage analytics and digital preservation

Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB)

- **Directory** of peer reviewed Open Access books and book publishers.
- The primary aim is to provide a **reliable source** for OA book metadata, OA publishers, to enhance discoverability, and maximize dissemination and visibility – **an industry resource uniting all Open Access Books**

OAPEN & DOAB: Synergies and Differences

DOAB Foundation

- Established as independent, non-profit foundation in 2019
- Partnership between OAPEN and OpenEdition
- Governance structure with stakeholder and scientific committees
- Introduced Library membership program
- Introducing Certification service for OA books and book publishers with OPERAS
- Redeveloping DOAB as open source platform on DSpace

SPRINGER NATURE

How you can help

OAPEN Library membership

<https://oapen.org/librarians/5972622-join-libraries>

OAPEN Membership through KU

<https://www.knowledgeunlatched.org/oapen/>

DOAB Library membership

DOAB Sponsorship

www.doabooks.org > support

SCOSS support <https://oapen.org/article/7832049-scoss-supports-oapen-and-doab>

Latest resource: OAPEN OA Books Toolkit

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `oabooks-toolkit.org`. The page features the OAPEN logo and a navigation menu with items like 'About OA', 'The OA Books landscape', 'About the Toolkit', 'Support', and 'Resources'. A prominent orange banner contains the title 'OAPEN OA Books Toolkit' and a brief description for authors. Below the banner are icons for 'Life cycle', 'FAQ', and 'Keywords'.

Home | OA Books Toolkit

oabooks-toolkit.org

open
Open Access
Publishing in European Networks

Life cycle FAQ Keywords Glossary

Home About OA The OA Books landscape About the Toolkit Support Resources

OAPEN
OA Books
Toolkit

For authors

This toolkit aims to help book authors to better understand open access book publishing and to increase trust in open access books. You will be able to find relevant articles on open access book publishing following the research lifecycle, by browsing frequently asked questions or by searching with keywords.

Life cycle FAQ Keywords

A scholarly infrastructure that provides
open bibliographic and citation data worldwide

Web

<http://opencitations.net>

Twitter

[@opencitations](https://twitter.com/opencitations)

Blog

<https://opencitations.wordpress.com>

OpenCitations: goals

OpenCitations has been established as a fully free and open infrastructure to provide access to global scholarly bibliographic and citation data, of quality and coverage to rival those from proprietary services, e.g. Clarivate Analytics' Web of Science (WoS) and Elsevier's Scopus

OpenCitations enables

- Fairness: it avoids institutions and independent scholars having to pay tens of thousands of dollars annually (that most of them cannot afford!) for commercial access to their own scholarly data
- Reuse: no license restrictions, since the data are provided under CC0, so users can republish and reuse for any purpose the citation data that OpenCitations provides
- Research assessment: by providing crucial data for national and international research evaluation exercises
- Governance: community involvement

OpenCitations: information and data

OpenCitations (<http://opencitations.net>) is an [independent infrastructure organization](#)

- dedicated to open scholarship and the **publication of open bibliographic and citation data** by the use of Semantic Web technologies
- engaged in advocacy for **open citations** and **open bibliographic metadata**

It provides:

- a data model: the [OpenCitations Data Model](#) (based on the [SPAR Ontologies](#))
- bibliographic and citation data (CC0): [OpenCitations Corpus](#), [COCI](#), [CROCI](#)
- software: in our [GitHub repository](#), released with open source licenses
- online services: [REST APIs](#), [SPARQL endpoints](#), [dumps](#) and [interfaces](#)

Using our data

We provide data containing more than 7 hundred million citations that the community can use for **any purpose**

Such data can be crucial as a vehicle for use in national and international research evaluation exercises to make such activities more **transparent and reproducible** as compared to other proprietary services

You can use our citation data (e.g. via our REST API) to **enhance or develop tools** to support your authors, researchers, students, institutional administrators, for instance by providing **metrics to monitor research** at your institution and by **improving the discoverability of research products** such as publications and data

Two ways to help

Ask your institution to **apply for membership** and thus support us financially

- Supporting membership (€500 - €8,000 per year)
Rights include: voting on the [OpenCitations](#) Council and to **elect candidates** to serve on the International Advisory Board for [OpenCitations](#)
- Development membership (€8,000 - €30,000 per year)
Rights include: Supporting membership rights + one **free registration** for next edition of Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata and **writing blog post** about your use of [OpenCitations](#) services and data on our blog
- Strategic membership (more than €30,000 per year)
Rights include: Development membership rights + a **seat on** the International Advisory Board for [OpenCitations](#)

Otherwise, ask your institution to fund us via **a donation**

More info (including the SCOSS flyer about us) at <http://opencitations.net/membership>

SCOSS & PKP

Sustaining Open Infrastructure

About us.

- The Public Knowledge Project (PKP) is a non-profit, research and open source software development initiative established in 1998 at the University of British Columbia (Canada).
- Today, its administrative home is at Simon Fraser University (Canada) and its research division is led from Stanford University (USA).
- Community governance structure via our international Advisory and Technical Committees.

What we do.

- Best known for creating and maintaining Open Journal Systems (OJS), the world's most widely used free and open source software for managing the editorial workflow and display of open access journal articles. Also develop and maintain Open Monograph Press (OMP) and Open Preprint Systems (OPS).
- Provide free documentation, free online courses, and free technical support for our users.

Why we do it.

- Increase the availability, accessibility, and quality of open access content.
 - Expand the diversity of voices and perspectives being heard in global scholarly communications.
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Why it matters.

- OJS is used by over 10,000 journals around the world in over 40 languages, including Norwegian.
- OJS is used as a national publishing portal in a number of countries, including Finland, Denmark, and Sweden, with more in progress.
- With over half of OJS journals in the Global South, it expands the diversity of voices participating in the scholarly conversation.
- OJS is the largest platform used by journals in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). More than 40% of journals indexed in the DOAJ identify OJS as their publishing platform.

Why we need your help.

- Creating and supporting open content is not free.
- The future of scholarly publishing is open access but this future should not be controlled by large commercial interests.
- Sustainable, affordable, community-controlled open access requires financial support for open infrastructures.

Why you should help.

PKP membership provides your institution with benefits, including participation on community governance committees, access to member-only events, and opportunities to provide direction on future software releases.

Your support helps to:

- Ensure free content continues to be available.
- Ensure locally-controlled, non-profit publishing can continue.
- Ensure our software continues to exist, to improve, and be part of the future.

How you can help.

To help fund the Public Knowledge Project (pkp.sfu.ca), contact:

Kevin Stranack
Membership Development & Community Education
kstranac@sfu.ca

See also SCOSS flyer with suggested funding level details: <https://scoss.org/help-sustain-open-infra/become-a-funder/>

Thank you for helping to sustain open.

Questions?